

European Commission Environment and Climate Programme 1994–98

Theme 3: Space Techniques Applied to Environmental Monitoring and Research

Area 3.3.3: Centre for Earth Observation Application Support

METOCEAN AND COASTAL ZONE MONITORING IN HARBOUR REGIONS USING SATELLITE RADAR

COASTMON

WP2: Development of improved EO data products

COASTMON report no. 2

NERSC Technical Report no. 156

April 1999

Authors:

Alastair D. Jenkins, Stein Sandven, Kees Mastenbroek, Magnar Reistad, Niamh Connolly, Torill Hamre, Deirdre Tobin, Eddie O'Leary, Bjørn Åge Hjollo, Lasse H. Pettersson, and Heidi Espedal

Contract No. ENV4-CT96-0360

<p>Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC)</p> <p>Edv. Griegsvei 3a N-5059 Bergen Norway</p> <p>Phone: +47 55 29 72 88 Fax: +47 55 20 00 50 e-mail: alastair.jenkins@nrsc.no</p>	<p>Advisory and Research Group on Geo Observation Systems and Services (ARGOSS)</p> <p>Voorsterweg 28 Marknesse, P.O. Box 61 8325 ZE Vollenhove The Netherlands</p> <p>Phone: +31 527 24 22 99 Fax: +31 527 24 20 16 e-mail: info@argoss.nl</p>
<p>Norwegian Meteorological Institute, Regional Division, Bergen (DNMI)</p> <p>Allégt. 70 N-5007 Bergen Norway</p> <p>Phone: +47 55 23 6600 Fax: +47 55 23 6703 e-mail: magnar.reistad@dnmi.no</p>	<p>Coastal Resources Centre, University College, Cork (CRC)</p> <p>Lee Maltings, Prospect Row Cork, Ireland</p> <p>Phone: +353 21 904 189 Fax: +353 21 277 922 e-mail: n.connolly@ucc.ie</p>

Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center Technical Report No. 156

<p>TITLE</p> <p>Metocean and Coastal Zone Monitoring in Harbour Regions using Satellite Radar — COASTMON</p> <p>WP2: Development of improved EO data products</p>	<p>REPORT IDENTIFICATION</p> <p>COASTMON Report No. 2 NERSC Technical Report No. 156</p>
<p>CLIENT</p> <p>CEC—DG XII</p> <p>CLIENT REFERENCE</p> <p>Tiziano Businaro, CEC—DG XII</p>	<p>CONTRACT</p> <p>ENV4-CT96-0360</p> <p>AVAILABILITY</p> <p>Open</p>
<p>INVESTIGATORS</p> <p>A. D. Jenkins, NERSC Stein Sandven, NERSC Kees Mastenbroek, ARGOSS Magnar Reistad, DNMI Niamh Connolly, CRC Torill Hamre, NERSC Deirdre Tobin, CRC Eddie O'Leary, CRC Bjørn Åge Hjollo, DNMI Lasse H. Pettersson, NERSC Heidi Espedal, NERSC</p>	<p>AUTHORISATION</p> <p>Bergen, April 1998</p> <p>DIRECTOR</p> <p>Ola M. Johannessen</p>

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Executive summary

The overall objective of COASTMON is to explore and test methods for use of synthetic aperture radar (SAR) and other new satellite data, and their integration with geographical information systems (GIS), in monitoring meteorological and oceanographic conditions in regions of heavy sea traffic, to improve navigational safety, to aid coastal zone management (CZM), and to improve utilization of satellite observations in the user community.

The project consists of four major Work Packages:

1. Identification of gaps between existing monitoring techniques for environmental conditions in coastal regions and requirements from the users.
2. Development of improved EO data products (wind, waves, currents, shallow water bathymetry, pollution, etc.) which include use of satellite data.
3. User demonstration in different test areas in Norway, Ireland and the Netherlands where satellite data will be obtained, analyzed and used together with other met-ocean data.
4. User assessment and recommendation for future use of satellite data in coastal regions.

This report presents the results of the studies in WP2. The aim of the products is to provide useful information for many different users such as weather forecasting services, coastal and harbour authorities with responsibilities for ship traffic, coastal management, etc., pollution authorities, fisheries and aquaculture, offshore industry, navy and coast guard, marine research and resources management, shipping and ferry companies, energy companies, coastal engineering firms, local government and planning authorities, leisure activities and education.

The work focused on five types of products: (1) high resolution wind fields from SAR, (2) spectral wave data from SAR, (3) wind and wave climatology from altimeter, (4) shallow water bathymetric charts, and (5) a group of SAR-derived products which map features such as currents, fronts and oil spills. In addition, the potential benefits of synergetic use of EO techniques in the analysis of selected ocean parameters was investigated, such as sea surface height and circulation features.

The main results of this Work Package are as follows:

- Develop and test an algorithm for deriving wind speed from SAR images were refined and used in the project, and comparison with modelled wind fields.
- A new algorithm for deriving spectral wave data from SAR image spectra was developed, and adapted to work for SAR image mode data. Both this new algorithm as well as earlier algorithms were tested in Norwegian and Irish coastal areas and compared with buoy data.
- A planning tool for marine operators and emergency response units was augmented with monthly statistics of wind and waves, which were integrated with a GIS at ARGOSS. Data from this system (CLAMS) were also made available online, through the Internet.
- The GIS based Wave Atlas for Ireland was also further developed in the project, allowing comparison of wave height data obtained from a numerical model (WAM) and remote sensing data (altimeter).
- The Bathymetry Assessment System (BAS) was enhanced and integrated with the Cork GIS for demonstrations in Irish waters. The inclusion of auxiliary data from the GIS helped the BAS users determine suitable locations for applying the bathymetry algorithm.

- Mapping of ocean fronts, eddies and current patterns has been demonstrated by SAR. Field observations have been used to document that frontal features in SAR images can be explained by gradients in the surface current field.
- SAR has also been used to observe natural surface slicks and man-made slicks such as oil spills. The wind speed is the main limiting factor, making observations difficult at wind speeds above 10 m/s.
- The Erim Ocean Model (EOM) was amended to take account of wave breaking processes generating extra centimetre-scale waves, but the initial analysis of model results indicated that further development of this model is needed to meet the user requirements.
- During the project period, DNMI used a wave model (WAM) for both high (10 km) and more coarse (50 km) resolution. The work in COASTMON contributed to the development of a data assimilation algorithm for altimeter data in this model. Further development and validation of DNMI's models will continue in other projects, such as EuroRose (MAST-III).

SAR is not the only important spaceborne instrument for observation of ocean processes. Therefore, existing algorithms were applied to generate products for algal bloom and sea surface temperature from AVHRR images using IR and optical channels. The main limiting factor for visual/IR data is the cloud cover. Synergetic remote sensing was attempted in a few cases, and the most promising result was for detection of large and meso-scale circulation features using SAR and thermal IR imagery. This combination of satellite data can provide useful complementary information which can be associated with bathymetric features.

The developed products were later used in WP3: User demonstrations, and evaluated in WP4: User assessment, conclusions and recommendations. The results of these Work Packages can be found in the Final Report for the COASTMON project.

1 Introduction and objectives

The overall objective of COASTMON is to explore and test methods for use of synthetic aperture radar (SAR) and other new satellite data, and their integration with geographical information systems (GIS), in monitoring environmental/met-ocean conditions in regions close to harbours trafficked by very large vessels, to improve navigational safety, to aid coastal zone management (CZM), and to improve utilization of satellite observations in the user community.

The coastal zone is an area of intense human activity, and phenomena and activities in the surrounding waters can be monitored with a number of earth observation techniques, including satellite radar. The project is exploring and testing methods to be used for monitoring areas adjacent to harbours with heavy ship traffic, in consultation with end users in the relevant areas. The methods include synthetic aperture radar and satellite altimeter observations, including those of wave height, current shear zones, wave-current interaction processes, and wind speed and direction, and it is aimed to integrate these observations into coastal monitoring, contingency planning, and planning of multi-user activities, using geographical information systems (GIS).

Coastal regions near ports, harbours, and other marine terminals are especially prone to environmental hazards owing to heavy traffic by very large crude-oil carriers (VLCCs), towed barges, and other vessels of deep draught and/or restricted maneuverability. Navigation in such regions can be difficult and hazardous, and it is critical to have in place an efficient system to monitor relevant met-ocean and water quality parameters in order to minimize the risk of accidents and to curtail damages in the event of an accident. Some harbour authorities have implemented Vessel Traffic Services (VTS) terminals with responsibilities including: pilotage; safety and regularity of marine traffic; emergency procedures; environmental concerns; communications, shore-to-ship-to-shore; and monitoring and prediction of meteorological and oceanographic (met-ocean) conditions.

The synthetic aperture radar (SAR) on the ERS satellite series has already shown its capability for detecting ships, oil slicks, and ocean structures related to spatial variability in the current, with promising results in several investigations on detecting and monitoring eddies, fronts, natural and man-made slicks and other ocean surface phenomena. However, further refinement of processing and interpretation techniques, and integration with other types of remote sensing and field data as well as numerical model results is required in order to produce viable products which can be offered to potential users in an operational context.

The incorporation of satellite as well as in situ observations into coastal zone management (CZM) plans will be greatly aided by an integrating of these data with GIS, to assist the safe development of harbour industrial activities. Data sets on aquaculture sites, fisheries resources, protected and sensitive habitats, navigation and mooring channels, mooring sites, port facilities, and coastal structures could thus all be integrated with remote sensing data. This would help in the development of an improved Vessel Traffic Service (VTS), which is in itself of paramount importance in CZM for the surrounding area.

Previous projects on met-ocean and environmental monitoring using satellite radar have mainly focused on monitoring the individual physical processes which will be studied in the current project. SAR can be used to detect the directional distribution of long-period wind waves, provided that a good first guess is provided from buoy measurements or a numerical model. It can also detect current fronts and eddies, although quantification of the current shear needs

further study. Changes in shallow-water bathymetry can be detected by SAR, and the technique has been verified in Dutch coastal waters. Satellite SAR has been shown to be capable of detecting natural surface films and oil spills, but further work needs to be done to distinguish the contributions from the various different phenomena. The use of SAR in monitoring coastal waters for oil spills has been verified in a pilot project, and state pollution control monitoring aircraft can be directed to suspected oil slicks visible in ERS SAR images.

2 Existing monitoring techniques and user requirement investigation

2.1 Existing monitoring techniques

Large-, regional- and meso-scale weather and ocean features in the European waters can be monitored by *polar orbiting* EO satellites with sensors operating in a wide range of the electromagnetic spectrum. *Passive* or *active microwave* sensors acquire data independent of daylight and clouds, ideal for high latitude observations of sea ice and climate change monitoring, but are also used to monitor wind, waves, ocean currents and oil spills. *Visual and infra-red (IR)* sensors monitor sea surface temperature, fronts, currents, eddies and ocean color. Small-scale features such as local pollution and floods can be monitored with *polar orbiting radar* and *high-resolution visual* satellite sensors. Figure 1 shows the temporal and spatial scales for a number of coastal zone processes and the capability of different satellite systems to cover these scales. Figure 2 gives a summary of sea surface features and processes observed by remote sensing techniques.

Examples of satellite-retrieved products and models which can be applied or developed for application within the defined goals of the COASTMON project include the following. For more details we refer the reader to the WP1 report [Jenkins *et al.*, 1997].

- Dynamical models for atmosphere and ocean (wind, temperature, sea surface elevation, waves, swell, currents), at grid resolutions as fine as 10 km.
- Wind speed from radar altimeter, wind speed/direction derived from microwave scatterometer, and being developed for SAR.
- Wave parameters: significant wave height from altimeter, wave direction and period from SAR.
- Sea surface temperature from infra-red radiometer sensors (NOAA AVHRR, ERS ATSR)
- Water quality parameters, including sediment, chlorophyll (CZCS, MOS, SeaWIFS), oil spill and natural surface film (SAR).
- Shallow-water bathymetry (SAR).
- Ship detection (SAR).

Figure 1: Overall illustration of the temporal and spatial scales of a variety of coastal zone parameters and processes, combined with coverage characteristics for relevant satellites and instruments (from [ESA, 1995]).

	Remote Sensing technique					
	Visible Near IR	Thermal IR	Passive Microw.	SAR	Radar Altimeter	Scatter- ometer
I Geophysical Variables & Features						
Temperature Fronts		X				
Current Fronts	X			#	#	
Meso-scale eddies	X	X		#	#	
Upwelling	X	X		#		
Wind Fronts				#		
Wind Speed			#	#	#	#
Wind Direction				#		#
Surface Waves				#	#	
Internal Waves				#		
II Water Quality						
Algae Blooms	X					
Surfactants	X			#		
Oil Spill	X	X		#		
Turbidity/Sediments	X					
III Sea Ice						
Ice Concentration	X		#	#		
Ice Types			#	#		#
Ice Motion	X			#		
Ice Edge	X	X	#	#	#	#

Figure 2: Sea surface features and processes observed by remote sensing techniques. X: cloud-free and/or daylight dependant, #: cloud and daylight independent.

3 COASTMON demonstration areas

The user requirements in the three study areas (Norwegian, Dutch and Irish coastal regions) have been identified by:

1. Established contacts with users of marine data through previous projects and ongoing services,
2. Dedicated user workshops in each of the three countries to define how satellite data best should be utilized to provide information which different users need, and
3. Extraction and synthesis of the main results from 1 and 2

Three user workshops were planned and arranged in Norway (Bergen), Ireland (Cork) and The Netherlands (at ARGOSS). Each workshop had participants from the main national users groups. In the workshops, representatives from many user groups expressed their opinions on what information they need from satellite data.

3.1 Norwegian location

The coastal region near Bergen is among the most trafficked areas in Norway where the most important traffic are tankers visiting the oil terminals in Mongstad and Sture. There are more than 2000 port-calls per year mostly by tankers which can be 300000 tones. The tankers have to sail through strong currents and narrow straits to enter the terminals, and during extreme weather conditions the steering of the large tankers can be difficult. The Fedje Ship Traffic Control Center is responsible for the ship traffic and is one of the main institutions in this region which needs information about wind, waves and currents. The centre is involved in COASTMON as one of the key users of satellite-based environmental information.

The main users of marine environmental data in the Norwegian coastal region are:

- Weather service
- Coastal authority
- Pollution Control Authority
- Fisheries and aquaculture
- Offshore industry
- Navy/Coast Guard

The Bergen regional division of the Norwegian Meteorological Institute (DNMI) is responsible for providing metocean data and forecasts to many users, and in particular to the offshore industry in the North Sea. DNMI uses satellite data in their weather forecasts as well as in other services such as wave forecast. The Nansen Center is working on development of satellite remote sensing techniques to observe sea surface and oceanographical parameters such as wind, waves, currents, fronts, eddies, temperature, chlorophyll, slick, and pollution. The centre has performed several user demonstration projects which have identified many gaps between user requirements and what satellite data can offer today.

3.2 Irish location

The Coastal Resources Centre (CRC) at the Coastal Zone Institute of University College Cork is investigating the interactions between physical and biological resources and human populations, with a view to establishing sustainable development, and thereafter, stimulate the adoption of scientifically-based integrated coastal zone management plans. CRC has developed extensive expertise in applications of GIS in the coastal zone. Several GIS systems have been developed for various customers: a wave energy information system for Ireland, a GIS for fisheries, socio-economic data and legislation, coastal zone management in Bantry Bay and more. CRC has therefore well-established contacts with many users of coastal and marine data in Ireland.

3.3 Netherlands location

The objectives of Dutch component of COASTMON are to involve key users in the Netherlands such as ship traffic management and other users of metocean data for demonstration of satellite data in marine monitoring and forecasting. The requirements for environmental information from several user groups are investigated. The user requirements will be used in COASTMON to further develop satellite data products, and demonstrate the feasibility of the products.

The monitoring and management the coastal zone, water resources and ship traffic is very important in the Netherlands. Several metocean remote sensing products are therefore being developed or used in the Netherlands. The most important are:

- *Assessment of bathymetry from Synthetic Aperture Radar images*

The Bathymetry Assessment System (BAS) has been developed to enable users to improve bathymetric maps using Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) pictures of coastal regions. Exploiting the fact that the bottom features modulate the radar backscatter via the small wind ripples, the system estimates the water depth variations. BAS is currently being used by Rijkswaterstaat and has been demonstrated to save costs.

- *High resolution wind fields from SAR images*

SAR images of coastal regions can also be used to assess the wind speed variations caused by a land-sea boundary. These wind speed variations are important for flooding risk assessments. Currently these assessments are based on modeling studies where the wave and water currents are being forced by a spatially homogeneous wind. With the help of the high resolution wind fields derived from SAR images, atmospheric boundary layer models that take into account the effects of the transition between land and water can be checked and improved. Using wind fields from these boundary layer models rather than uniform wind fields will improve the quality of the flooding risk assessment.

- *The assessment of the wind and wave climate using spaceborne microwave sensors*

This application is not limited to the Dutch coastal waters, but it is nevertheless important to Dutch companies operating world wide. These companies have expressed a pressing need for wind and wave climate assessments in areas where no buoy records are available. The on-line wind and wave climate assessment system will enable offshore industry user to make estimates of the offshore climate of any part of the global coastal seas. The wind and wave climate estimates are based on satellite observations with an

array of different sensors: altimeter, scatterometer and SAR. After the user specifies his region of interest, all wind and wave observations made in this region over the past decade by several satellites (Geosat, ERS-1, ERS-2, Topex/Poseidon) are collected from a database. Subsequently the user is enabled to process the data according to his particular requirements.

ARGOSS (Advisory and Research Group on Geo Observation Systems and Services) offers products and services to provide end users with environmental information they need, using satellite data in combinations with models and in situ data. A main objective of ARGOSS is to bridge the gap which often exists between research and end users requirements for information. One of the most important products provided by ARGOSS is a method for shallow water bathymetry measurements using SAR data. ARGOSS is focused on the needs for the coastal and marine user community and has therefore good contact with many of these users.

3.4 Summary of user requirement investigation

The user requirement investigation is described in detail in COASTMON report no. 1 [Jenkins *et al.*, 1997].

Table 1 summarizes the information requirements for the main users in Norway, and the Fedje VTS centre requirements are detailed in Table 2. Requirements from some key users in the Netherlands are listed in Table 3.

Table 1: Summary of information requirements for the main users in Norway.

User Type	Example	Need for information	Satellite products
Weather service	DNMI, Western Norway	surface wind wave spectra significant wave height	Scatterometer- and SAR-derived wind; SAR wave spectra; altimeter wave height
Coastal authority	Fedje Ship Traffic Control Centre	Wave, current and pollution data	SAR wave spectra, SAR wind fields, eddy and frontal maps combining SAR and other data, surface current fields from altimeter and models
Pollution authority	State Pollution Control Authority	Location of pollution events	SAR data showing potential oil spills
Fisheries and aquaculture	Fisheries Directorate	Environmental statistics and location of fishing vessels	SAR ship location maps; Statistics; wave climatology, frontal maps, SST, currents
	Individual fishing vessels	Weather and wave forecast	Ocean front maps, wave spectra
	Fish farmers	No environmental information is used except in specific situations of extreme temperatures, algal blooms, etc.	Ocean front maps, SST
Offshore industry	Oil companies: Statoil, Shell, etc.	Drilling and production in deep waters with floating constructions requires better information about currents and eddies	Surface currents from altimeter, ocean frontal maps from SAR and AVHRR
Navy / Coastguard	vessels and headquarters	Location of fishing vessels, currents, eddies, fronts, temperature, sound velocity, general monitoring of oceanographic conditions	SST maps, ocean frontal maps from SAR and AVHRR, currents from altimeter

Table 2: Summary of requirements from the Fedje VTS Centre.

Required product	Current status	Data and model input
Surface current	Not available from satellite data in the near-coastal region. Altimeter data provides barotropic currents in open ocean. High resolution ocean models, combined with SAR for localization of fronts and eddies, can be useful. Ocean Surface Current Radar mounted on land, also in combination with SAR, seems to be the most promising remote sensing technique.	Wind fields from models; Current fields from models; Surface slope from altimeter; SAR images
Eddies and fronts	SAR in combination with AVHRR can be used to map the location and propagation of eddies and fronts, but do not provide quantitative velocities. Ocean models can simulate eddies and fronts if they have sufficient resolution and relevant input data. Operational ocean models with typical 50 km resolution do not resolve eddies and fronts	SAR and AVHRR data; High-resolution ocean models
Wave height	Available from altimeter data, but not near land and with poor resolution in open ocean. Available from wave models. SAR wave spectra can be used as input to the models	Wave models; Altimeter; SAR data: input to models
Wave length and direction	Wave models provide the whole spectrum, SAR can give the longer waves (i.e. above 50 - 100 m). SAR provide high spatial resolution and information in fjords, straits and near the coast.	SAR images; Wave models
Wave period	Wave models provide the whole spectrum. SAR can give input to the models	Wave models; SAR data: input to models
Surface wind velocity	Can be obtained from scatterometer (coarse resolution, i.e. 50–100 km) and from SAR (fine resolution i.e. 5–10 km). Wind speed can also be obtained from altimeter. Atmospheric models provides wind fields at resolution of typically 50 km, depending on model resolution.	Scatterometer; Altimeter, SAR
Ship detection	Location of ships outside the radar range would be useful if available in real time	SAR
Oil spill detection	Identification of oil spills in real time will be useful, especially if the information can be used to proved which ships have cause the pollution	SAR
Other environmental parameters: SST, water colour, etc.	With increasing responsibility for environmental monitoring the Fedje Centre would need information about temperature, chlorophyll and other ocean colour information as supplement to current and wave data.	AVHRR/ATSR, SeaWIFS

Table 3: Some key users and requirements for The Netherlands.

User	Activity	Requirements	Products
KNMI	Ship traffic management	Bathymetry, high-resolution wind fields	Wind (scatterometer, cloud tracking)
Rijkswaterstaat	Operational forecasts (Approaches to Rotterdam and Antwerp harbours)		Waves (altimeter), swell (SAR) Visibility (NOAA, MeteoSat) Sediment transport (NOAA, MOS, SeaWIFS)
Shell International	Oil industry. Exploration of (edge of) continental shelves around the world	Distributions of wind speed/direction Sig. wave height, swell period/energy/direction Joint statistics of wave period and energy	Altimeter, scatterometer SAR wave mode (spectral data not available at present) Buoy records at a limited no. of locations Wave models may be poor
Teamwork Technology	Wave power	High-spatial resolution average wave height along coast of Portugal	Altimeter Global wave models too coarse Buoy records for validation Available information needs to be processed appropriately
Rijkswaterstaat	Management of Dutch coastal waters	Water quality: temperature, suspended matter, chlorophyll Bathymetry: regular monitoring	NOAA, SeaWIFS, MOS SAR
Heeremac	Transportation of oil platforms Laying of pipelines Continental shelves around the world	Climatology of wave spectra to calculate vessel motion response	SAR (but spectral data not available at present) Buoy data used if available. Ship measurements too poor Swell from numerical models not adequate

4 Data products developed

Based on the discussions with the potential end users, the user workshops held in Norway, Ireland, and the Netherlands, and the EO products available to the project partners, the following products, as refined and further developed, are presented in this report:

1. High resolution wind fields from SAR
 - The use of wind analysis from EO data in conjunction with numerical models
 - High resolution wind fields from SAR, over Dutch coastal areas
2. Spectral wave data from SAR
 - SAR wave spectra from the Norwegian study area
 - Transition of wave spectra going inshore (Irish study area)
3. Wind and wave climatology
 - Wave climate data visualization for operational planning
 - Intercomparison of wave model results and altimeter wave heights
 - Global wave climate assessment system
4. Bathymetry assessment
 - Application of the Bathymetry Assessment System (BAS) in the Rosslare area
 - Seasonal maps identifying locations suitable for the application of the BAS technique
5. Currents, fronts, and water quality
 - Current model results and comparison using EO
 - Sea surface temperature and ocean frontal features
 - Algal bloom, natural film and oil spill monitoring
 - Synergy of EO techniques

4.1 High resolution wind fields from SAR

4.1.1 Introduction and technical description

One of the most important physical parameters in the coastal zones and harbour regions is the wind field. Due to the nearby presence of land, the wind field shows a large spatial variability in these regions. With the help of radar images made by the ERS Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) an overview of the spatial distribution of the wind can be obtained. Within the COASTMON project this technique will be further refined, and it will be applied to coastal regions along the Irish, Norwegian and Dutch coasts.

Wind observations made with radar altimeters and scatterometers made over the open ocean are now routinely used to improve the description of the atmosphere in numerical weather prediction models. The spatial resolution of these radars, which varies from 10 km for the altimeter to 50 km for the scatterometer, makes them of little use in coastal areas. Due to the presence of land-sea transitions, the wind varies on much smaller scales in these regions. However, for some applications knowledge of these near-coast variations is important. To determine the design height of dikes and barriers, for example, detailed information on the structure of the near shore wind field is required. By analyzing images made with a Synthetic Aperture Radar, for instance of the European ERS satellites, these data can be obtained.

Both the SAR and the scatterometer on the ERS satellites are vertically polarized C-band radars. For this reason the relation between the back scattered power and the wind speed that has been determined for the scatterometer can also be used to interpret the SAR images. The CMOD-4 wind retrieval model described in [Stoffelen and Anderson, 1993] is developed for the ERS-1 C-band scatterometer but it is also shown to give good estimates of wind speed [Johannessen *et al.*, 1994, Vachon and Dobson, 1996, Vachon *et al.*, 1995] when applied to ERS-1 SAR images. The model was developed for deep sea conditions, and is running operationally at several meteorological centres.

Another method to derive the wind speed from SAR is based on the spectral properties of the image. The SAR wind algorithm (SWA) proposed by Vachon *et al.* [Vachon *et al.*, 1994] and further examined by Chapron *et al.* [Chapron *et al.*, 1995] and Korsbakken *et al.* [Korsbakken *et al.*, 1998], is based on a relation between the smearing effects [Hasselmann and Shemdin, 1982] in the SAR image and the wind field. Smearing effects tend to increase the coherence (correlation) length of the radar returns in the spatial image domain and to influence the spectral properties of the SAR image.

The SWA is derived from a comparison of ERS SAR wave-mode data and the ERS wind scatterometer data which can be simultaneously acquired with the same satellite. In the case of a fully developed sea (no fetch limitation), the empirical SWA relation, based on an evaluation of 1200 SAR wave-mode imagerettes with a central incidence angle of 20.2 degrees, is given by [Chapron *et al.*, 1995] as

$$U_{10} = 4.75 \left(\frac{\lambda_c - 30}{110} \right) \text{ m s}^{-1},$$

where U_{10} is the wind speed at 10 m above the surface and λ_c is the azimuth cutoff wavelength.

The methods of retrieving high resolution wind fields from SAR images which is illustrated here can be seen as complementary to the conventional wind observations from platforms and buoys. Where the conventional observations give an overview of the development of the wind with time on a limited set of locations, the SAR provides a good spatial overview on a limited number of occasions. In the case of the IJsselmeer, about one SAR image of the ERS satellites (operational since 1991) is available every two weeks. Analysis of in-situ wind measurements in combination with the high resolution SAR wind fields will lead to a better description of the wind climate in near shore regions, and hence to better estimates of the extreme wave heights and storm surges.

Like the scatterometer the SAR is a side looking radar, and both make all weather radar images of the ocean surface. By using an intricate processing of the return signal, the SAR is able to observe details that are as small as 100 m, where the scatterometer has a resolution of 50 km. The scatterometer, which is specifically designed to observe the wind above the ocean,

uses three separate radar beams which each point in a different direction. Combining the information from these three different observations, the scatterometer is able to work out both the speed and the direction of the wind. As the SAR has only one beam, a different procedure has to be used to determine the wind direction. Owing to its high resolution, the SAR is often able to resolve the wind streaks caused by the turbulence in the lower part of the atmosphere. Vachon and Dobson automated this procedure by determining the wind direction from the low wave number part of the SAR spectrum. They found they could retrieve the wind speed and direction with an accuracy of 1.5 m/s and 24° , respectively, for winds between 3 and 12 m/s (with a 180° ambiguity). In the image shown in Figure 3 the streaks, which are aligned with the wind direction, are clearly visible. When the direction of the wind is determined, the distribution of the wind speed is calculated from the power of the back scattered radar signal in a similar fashion as is done with the scatterometer. The wind direction can also be estimated from the CMOD4 model for different incidence angles, provided the wind speed, derived from the SWA method, can be associated with the corresponding measured radar backscatter (σ^0).

In such cases, four solutions, i.e., two pairs, each with a 180° ambiguity, can be found, except in the cases when the direction is close to upwind (the wind blowing toward the radar) or downwind, for which only one pair is found. (Note that for the three beam scatterometers on ERS-1 and ERS-2 the number of solutions is reduced to a single pair with a 180° ambiguity.). Example of wind vectors derived from SAR are shown in Figure 4.

4.1.2 High resolution wind field from SAR, over Dutch coastal areas

To demonstrate the capabilities of the spaceborne SAR systems to retrieve high resolution wind fields in coastal areas, six ERS-1 SAR images acquired over Dutch coastal waters have been analyzed:

- IJsselmeer, February 16, 1995
- Waddenzee, May 13, 1994
- Waddenzee, August 12, 1994
- Dutch coast, June 23, 1995
- Dutch coast, July 2, 1995
- Dutch coast, July 9, 1995

These analyses are shown in Figure 5.

Original SAR data © ESA 1995

Figure 3: ERS SAR image of IJsselmeer (left), and the distribution of the wind speed derived from the image (right).

Original SAR data © ESA 1995

Figure 4: Wind field derived from an ERS-1 SAR image (left) on September 17, 1995. Wind speed ranges from 7 to 13 m/s. SAR wind vectors derived from two SAR passes, each 300 by 100 km, off the coast of southwest Norway. Red arrows indicate the standard meteorological analysis points.

Figure 5: Wind speed analysis for ERS SAR images

Top left: IJsselmeer, 1995 Feb 6. Top right: Waddenzee, 1994 May 13

Middle left: Waddenzee, 1994 May 13. Middle right: Dutch coast, 1995 June 23

Bottom left: Dutch coast, 1995 July 2. Bottom right: Dutch coast, 1995 July 9

Figure 6: Wind at 10 m above surface from the operational HIRLAM model with 50 km resolution, 1998 February 10, 06h UTC (6-hour forecast). The small symbols are observations.

4.1.3 Wind analysis from SAR data as supplement to numerical models

Figures 6–7 show examples of meteorological wind data products from operational and experimental atmospheric models. The results of these models are fed into wave models described in section 4.2, and current models described in section 4.5.

Examples of coastal wind retrieval from SAR in the Norwegian study area are shown in Figure 8, where wind speed is obtained in 10×10 km squares, using the CMOD-4 algorithm. The locations of simultaneous wind measurements (Hellesøy, an island south of Fedje, and the Troll oil/gas field) are marked.

Figure 9 show a ERS-2 SAR image of the Norwegian study area, in which the wind is relatively light and bright regions of swell wave breaking can be seen on the exposed coasts. At the mouth of Sognefjord in the top right of the picture, the wind is stronger and there appears to be a jet of stronger winds blowing out of it. This is consistent with the observed wind direction which was easterly at an island station and north-easterly at the offshore Troll gas field.

The data were obtained from Tromsø Satellite Station as fast delivery products (full and low resolution images). It was not possible with these products to apply the proper correction for the saturation of the ERS analogue-to-digital conversion, and so there are some inaccuracies in the computed winds—the errors are greatest at near range for large wind speeds. Consequently, the wind speeds are inaccurate, particularly for January 4 near Hellesøy.

Figure 7: Wind at 10 m above surface from the experimental HIRLAM model with 10 km resolution, 1998 February 10, 06h UTC (6-hour forecast). Note the strengthening of the wind near Stad compared to the 50 km model, and the position of Sognefjord and Fedje.)

Figure 8: Left: Wind speed in m/s, using the CMOD-4 algorithm, from ERS SAR data for the Norwegian location, 1997 December 19 at 11h UTC. Atmospheric model predictions: Wind speed SE 2.5–5 m/s Observations—Troll: NE 3 m/s; Hellesøy: E 3 m/s
 Right: Wind speed in m/s, using the CMOD-4 algorithm, from ERS SAR data for the Norwegian location, 1998 January 4 Atmospheric model predictions: Wind speed S 13 m/s Observations—Troll: SSW 10 m/s; Hellesøy: SSE 13 m/s

Original SAR data © ESA/TSS 1997

Figure 9: Low-resolution ERS-2 SAR image of the West Norwegian coast, 1997 December 19.

4.2 Wave data products

Significant wave height is available from satellite altimeter data and this is used in wave forecasts by DNMI [Breivik and Reistad, 1992]. An example of significant wave height forecast for the North Atlantic and Norwegian Sea is shown in Figure 10. Also, directive wave spectrum and wave period can be estimated, as shown in Figure 11 where also the modelled wave spectra are compared with a coastal wave radar located at Fedje.

Information on the directional wave spectrum can be obtained from SAR images, by an inversion technique which normally uses a ‘first guess’ wave spectrum, based, for example, on the wind-wave spectrum associated with the local wind field obtained from model results. Such methods have been described in e.g. [Hasselmann and Hasselmann, 1991] and [Krogstad, 1992, Krogstad *et al.*, 1994].

To investigate the capability of the SAR to image waves propagating into harbour areas, it is difficult to use a wave model. For each area that is to be analysed, a wave model has to be set up, and for each image a wave model runs needs to be executed. This would make this method too expensive to be of any practical use. Hence a retrieval algorithm is needed that is capable of interpreting a SAR image spectrum without any a priori knowledge about the sea state.

In the past year ARGOSS has developed such an algorithm. Rather than a 1st guess wave spectrum, it uses an estimate of the local wind. The method has been validated using the SAR wave mode data set acquired by the ERS-1 and ERS-2 missions. Unlike the data obtained with the SAR in image mode, the data acquired in the wave mode have a global coverage. By collocating the SAR wave mode spectra with buoy records (in particular those measured by the American NOAA buoys) we were able to construct a data set large enough to derive some

Figure 10: Significant wave height from the WINCH model, 1998 February 10, 06h UTC (6-hour forecast).

Figure 11: Directional wave spectrum from the wave radar at Fedje, and from the WINCH wave model, on 1998 February 10.

Figure 12: Validation of the ARGOSS SAR wave spectra retrieval algorithm. Shown here is the retrieved height of the waves with periods longer than 12 seconds (225 m).

statistics about the retrieval method. In the scatter plot of Figure 12, the retrieved height of the waves longer than 12 seconds (i.e. wavelength longer than about 225 m) is shown as a function of the height observed by 11 NOAA buoys. The SAR is capable of retrieving the height of these long waves with a 25 % accuracy.

The following example is based on the older technique [Krogstad, 1992, Krogstad *et al.*, 1994], with an initial ‘first guess’ spectrum which is in fact chosen rather arbitrarily. Nevertheless, the resulting inverted spectra are in reasonable agreement with observations, as well as reproducing the swell waves apparent in the SAR image.

4.2.1 SAR wave spectra from the Norwegian study area

An example of a Full Resolution SAR image (.FRI) obtained from the Fedje area is shown in Figure 13 ¹. The image has 5000×6300 pixels, each covering $20 \text{ m} \times 16 \text{ m}$. Wave spectra have been calculated from several subimages, each consisting of 512×512 pixels. Examples of subimages and corresponding wave spectra are reproduced in Figure 14.

The wave spectra shown in Figure 15 are obtained using the inversion technique, from 256×256 -pixel subimages. There is approximate agreement with model results. WINCH wave model computations indicate the presence of a northward-propagating swell with significant height 1.2m, see Figure 16. The predicted total significant wave height was 1.4m, but the SAR inversion is not generally particularly reliable in predicting absolute wave heights.

¹The figures in this section were produced using the GMT mapping software [Wessel and Smith, 1991], which is available free of charge from the University of Hawaii. In Unix, type ‘echo "information gmtgroup" | mail listserver@soest.hawaii.edu’, to get a download shell script [Wessel and Smith, 1995]. The package permits the plotting of datasets onto maps in a large variety of projections. A comprehensive global coastline and river database, and also a free interactive graphical user interface (IGMT), are available.

Original SAR data © ESA/TSS 1997

Figure 13: Full Resolution SAR image (.FRI) covering a 100 × 100 km area on the coast of western Norway, obtained from Tromsø Satellite Station, at 11h UTC on 1997 December 19. The island of Fedje and the oil refinery at Mongstad (appearing as a bright region) are marked. The numbered rectangles are reproduced, enlarged, in Figure 14.

Original SAR data © ESA/TSS 1997

Figure 14: Enlarged reproductions of the rectangular parts marked off on the image of Figure 13. The wave spectra from the rectangles marked 'WS (number)', obtained from SAR inversion, are shown in Figure 20.

Figure 15: Wave spectra obtained by SAR inversion, for the rectangles marked off on Figure 14. The wavenumber axes are in the SAR range and azimuth directions, parallel to the edges of the image. Note that wave spectra 1 and 2 are corrupted by the presence of land in the image. The vertically-aligned dark streaks in WS 3, 5 and 6 may be causing the apparent range-directed wavenumber component at around 200 m wavelength. The azimuth-directed wave components with wavelengths shorter than 200 m correspond to the observed swell in the image.

Original SAR data © ESA/TSS 1997

Figure 16: Norwegian location, 1997 December 19.

Top left: 12-hour forecast for wind from HIRLAM atmospheric model with 50 km resolution, December 19, 12h UTC

Top right: 12-hour forecast for wind from HIRLAM atmospheric model with 10 km resolution

Bottom left: Significant wave height forecast from WAM wave model

Bottom right: ERS SAR image taken at 11h UTC.

Forecast for Fedje location, Meteorological analysis, HIRLAM/WINCH: Wind: SE 5m/s, Hs: 1.4m, Tz: 7s, Swell: 1.2m, 9s from South

Observations: Troll NE 3m/s, 2.5m, 7s. Hellisøy (the island just south of Fedje): E 3 m/s

4.2.2 Transition of wave spectra going inshore (Irish study area)

When long swell waves approach the shore, they are often affected by the local bathymetry. This may give rise to a number of phenomena, such as shoaling, refraction and breaking. The ability of a space borne SAR sensor to measure wave spectra provides an opportunity to get a spatial overview of the spatial evolution of wave field when it approaches the shore line. In the COASTMON project an algorithm is developed to retrieve ocean wave spectra from SAR image spectra. This algorithm specifically aimed at processing the global SAR wave mode archive in order to add spectral wave information to metocean climate assessments. Here this method is adapted to handle SAR spectra derived from SAR data acquired in the so-called image mode².

Technical description

The retrieval algorithm developed to exploit the SAR wave mode archive acquired by the ERS-1 and ERS-2 missions combines the SAR measurements with wind vectors from the scatterometer [Mastenbroek and De Valk 1998]. This is done to obtain information on the level of the wave components not resolved by the SAR which determine the azimuth cutoff. However, when the SAR onboard the ERS satellites is in image mode the scatterometer is switched off. There are several solutions possible to this problem. In this present version we will use wind information from other sources like nearby weather stations to obtain the local wind conditions at the time the image was recorded. In a next version we would like to exploit the fact that the radar backscatter from the ERS-1/2 SAR images is calibrated, and can be related to the wind vector. In strong wind conditions, when the longest wind wave components are resolved by the SAR, the combination of radar backscatter and SAR spectrum may suffice to determine both the wind speed and its direction.

To obtain a collection of ocean wave spectra from a SAR image the following steps are taken:

1. The PRI SAR image product which is used for the present version gives the 3-look normalised radar backscatter amplitude on a grid with a spacing of 12.5 m. In the first step the 100 by 100 km image is divided into 5 by 5 km blocks. After visual inspection of the image a number of these sub-images can be selected for further processing (see Figure 17).
2. Using the procedure described by Laur et al. [Laur *et al.*, 1996] the PRI image is re-calibrated. This involves compensating for the power loss in the AD converter of the ERS satellites, that can lead to an underestimation of the radar backscatter of up to 6 dB. The normalised radar backscatter over open water is related to the wind speed, wind direction and the incidence angle of the radar.
3. The selected 5 by 5 km sub-images are read from CD-ROM and averaged to a 25 by 25 m resolution. The power spectra of the radar backscatter are stored in an ASCII file together with some ancillary data such as the incidence angle and the satellite heading.
4. The SAR image power spectra are transformed to ocean wave spectra by inverting the nonlinear mapping relations proposed in [Hasselmann and Hasselmann, 1991].

An example of a SAR sub-image showing a swell system is shown in Figure 18.

²<http://earth1.esrin.esa.it/f/eo3.298/ERS1.3.2>

Original SAR data © ESA 1992

Figure 17: A SAR image acquired on 19 December 1992 of the South coast of Ireland. The nine selected sub-images are indicated.

Original SAR data © ESA 1992

Figure 18: Sub-image cut out from the SAR image shown in Figure 17. The sub-image corresponds to the spot marked 1 in Figure 17.

Product examples

The above method has been applied to a SAR image acquired on December 19, 1992, of the Irish south coast (see Figure 17). The image shows swell waves entering from the South. The spectra of the nine selected sub-images are shown in Figure 19. The radar backscatter shows that the wind speed at the time of the image acquisition was low: between 3 and 5 m/s. Using this wind speed the SAR spectra were converted into the ocean wave spectra shown in Figure 20.

The results show that we are dealing with two separate swell systems. The first is coming on from the West and has a peak wave length of about 180 m. The Northern most selected areas (sub-images 1-3) are sheltered from these waves. The second swell system is coming in from the South and is visible in all 9 selected sites. The waves of this system are a little longer, with a peak wave length of about 250 to 300 m. It appears that the amplitude of the wave components of this swell system traveling in the range direction is exaggerated. This is particularly clear in spectrum 7. The overestimation of these range traveling waves is probably caused by an underestimation of the RAR contribution to the modulation transfer function. The dominating modulation mechanism for waves with a component in the azimuth direction is the velocity bunching caused by the Doppler shifting of the return signal by the orbital velocity of the waves. This mechanism is well understood. For waves traveling exactly in the range direction this mechanism does not contribute. For these waves only the tilt and hydrodynamical modulation mechanisms contribute. The size and phase of, in particular, the latter is not well known.

Figure 19: The nine SAR image spectra corresponding to the locations marked in Figure 17.

Figure 20: The ocean wave spectra derived from the SAR image spectra shown in Figure 19.

4.2.3 Global wave climate assessment system by SAR

Introduction

One of the outcomes of the Dutch user requirements workshop (held at May 5, 1997 at ARGOSS) was that the Dutch users see the largest potential for remote sensing products in assessing the situation in remote areas. Apart from the bathymetry assessment system, which seems to have a large potential in Dutch coastal waters, most other applications that remote sensing techniques can be put to have viable, conventional alternatives. This includes the assessment of the wind and wave climate from satellite data. The climate data can be derived cheaply and accurately from a buoy network that has been operated in the Southern part of the North Sea over the past decades.

However, the offshore consultancy companies indicated that the bulk of their work involves remote coastal areas outside the Dutch coastal waters. In the majority of these areas no climate data is available. It is clear that remote sensing products, with their global coverage, could be very useful here.

In conversations with end users following the workshop it was established that the requirements for metocean climate data fall in different categories:

- Wave height and wind speed at given location and time, for instance to investigate conditions that led to an accident. Now the service exists, it is also used for other purposes, such as the assessment whether the conditions at any given time and place are favorable for the detection of an oil spill with SAR imagery.
- Capability to make on-line wind and wave climate assessments, in particular to assist in the estimation of the expected downtime during an operation. These assessments have to be made in order to establish the financial risks during the tendering phase.
- Tailored wind and wave climate tables for a given location (on paper and digital). For the actual planning of offshore operations, but also to run morphological models, users often prefer to define the exact format of the climate data they want to receive.

It was also indicated that for the latter two products, i.e. the wind and wave climate assessments, spectra wave climate data was essential. The only satellite sensor that can provide these data is the Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR). Over the past 6 years, the ERS-1 and ERS-2 satellites have collected an archive of SAR image spectra from which ocean wave spectra can be derived. This dataset has a global coverage, and the density of measurements is sufficient to allow climate estimates. In the scope of COASTMON an algorithm has been developed to retrieve ocean wave climate data from these SAR measurements. This algorithm has been applied to all recorded SAR wave mode observations, and the results have been used to set up both the online climate system CLAMS, and an offline climate service.

Technical description

The way in which an ocean wave spectrum is mapped onto a SAR spectrum is reasonably well understood. Hasselmann and Hasselmann [Hasselmann and Hasselmann, 1991], hereafter referred to as HH91, have derived a closed set of equations, in which the SAR image spectrum

is given as an expansion series in the ocean wave spectrum. The reason for this nonlinear dependence is that the orbital velocities of the waves interfere with the way in which the SAR constructs its resolution in the azimuth direction. To retrieve an ocean wave spectrum from an observed SAR spectrum means that this nonlinear relation has to be inverted.

The standard method to do this inversion is to start with a first guess wave spectrum, usually from a numerical wave model, and to change this spectrum iteratively until its associated SAR spectrum matches the observed SAR spectrum. A retrieval scheme along these lines is described by HH91. *Krogstad et al.* [Krogstad *et al.*, 1994] developed a simplified method that ignores the nonlinearities in the SAR mapping.

The above mentioned retrieval algorithms are not optimally suited for the derivation of spectral wave climate data. First of all, both methods reject a sizable fraction of the observed SAR spectra: *Heimbach et al.* [Heimbach *et al.*, 1998] reports a rejection percentage of 30 % using the HH91 retrieval method, according to *Breivik et al.* [Breivik *et al.*, 1998] the method of *Krogstad et al.* [Krogstad *et al.*, 1994] rejects half of the available SAR observations. It is clear that the rejection of such large portions of data has a detrimental effect on the wave climate statistics to be derived from the observations. A second disadvantage of both methods is their dependence on the presence of a first guess wave spectrum. For the present purpose, a global wave climate atlas, this is impractical: to generate all necessary wave spectra would require running a global wave model for the whole 6 year period since 1991.

The method developed in the COASTMON project does not require *a priori* knowledge of the sea state to retrieve an ocean wave spectrum for a SAR observation. Instead, the fact that on the ERS satellites the scatterometer is operated simultaneously with the SAR wave mode is exploited. As the SAR measurement is located inside the scatterometer swath, each SAR wave mode spectrum can be associated with a wind vector from the scatterometer. Using a standard parameterization, a first guess wave spectrum is constructed. The stage of development and the exact propagation direction of the wind sea are found by minimizing the difference between the SAR spectrum calculated from the wind sea and the observed SAR spectrum. The residual signal in the observed SAR spectrum is interpreted as swell, and is translated from the SAR spectral domain into the wave spectral domain assuming the mapping relations for these long waves are linear. A more detailed account of the retrieval algorithm is given in Mastenbroek and De Valk [Mastenbroek and de Valk, 1998].

In Figure 21 the relative quality of the retrieved spectra in different frequency bands is compared. The energy in the shortest wave components, with wave periods between 10 and 13 seconds, is slightly underestimated. This may be caused by the azimuth cutoff, which obviously has its largest effect on the shortest wave components. The performance of the system is optimal for waves with a period between 13 and 16 seconds. The relative error in the retrieval of the height of these waves is 32 %, the standard deviation is 0.32 m. For waves with periods longer than 16 seconds the standard deviation is even smaller, 0.26 m, but given the limited amount of energy in this frequency band, the relative performance is worse (44 %).

The above method has been compared to the one described by HH91 for 142 spectra acquired by the ERS-1 on January 30, 1993. No independent in situ data are available for these cases. The retrieved wave heights show good agreement. However, this is not the case for the underlying two dimensional spectra. This is illustrated by examples shown in the Figures 22 and 23. These two particular cases are also discussed in [Hasselmann *et al.*, 1996]: the first case corresponds to their Figure 1 and 4b, the second with their Figure 7.

Figure 21: Retrieval of the height of the waves in three different frequency bands: (a) wave period between 10 and 13 seconds (length between 150 and 250 m); (b) wave period between 13 and 16 seconds (length between 250 and 400 m) and (c) waves with periods longer than 16 seconds (400 m in deep water).

Figure 22 shows a case where a 10 m/s wind is blowing in the negative azimuth direction. In the WAM model the associated wind sea peak has a peak wave length of 30 m (see Figure 1 in [Hasselmann *et al.*, 1996]), which falls outside the domain shown in figure 22. The SAR spectrum observed by the ERS-1 is very noisy, the signal to noise ratio is only 2.6, and the energy is distributed along the range axis in a slightly skewed way. This spectrum is interpreted completely differently by both schemes. The MPI algorithm matches the observed SAR spectrum by redistributing energy between three different swell systems, whereas the SPRA method concludes there are no swell present at all. The latter scheme explains the low wavenumber signal in the observed SAR spectrum as the nonlinear bands caused by a fully developed, azimuth traveling wind sea. This option is not available to the MPI scheme, as it uses a quasilinear approximation to calculate which changes to the wave spectrum would improve the match with the observed SAR spectrum. Which of the two schemes produced the wave spectrum closest to reality is not known, as no in situ data are available.

A second example is shown in Figure 23, a case also discussed in [Hasselmann *et al.*, 1996] (their Figure 7). The observed SAR spectrum shows a clear peak, with a wave length of 200 m. The SPRA scheme matches this peak with a slightly underdeveloped ($U_{10}/c_p=1.2$) wind sea, propagating in the wind direction as detected by the scatterometer. Given the consistency between the SAR spectrum and the observed wind, this solution seems very probable. The scatterometer wind direction differs about 40° from the one in the meteorological model that is used to force the wave model. As the MPI scheme relies on the WAM model spectrum, this clearly influences the outcome of the inversion. As it can not match the peak caused by the wind sea in the wave model, the level of this peak is diminished. To explain the peak in the SAR spectrum a swell system is created that is propagating exactly upwind. This example shows that the dependence of the MPI scheme on the WAM model first guess goes beyond merely the elimination of the 180° ambiguity in the propagation direction of the waves.

Figure 22: Comparison with the retrieval algorithm developed by the Max Planck Institute (MPI) in Hamburg for a SAR spectrum acquired on January 30, 1993 at 11:38Z in the South Atlantic near the islands of South Georgia (51S, 32W). First column: first guess from the wave model WAM; second column: spectra retrieved with MPI scheme; third column: observed SAR spectrum and wind vector; fourth column: spectra retrieved with the SPRA scheme. This example corresponds with Figures 1 and 4b in [Hasselmann *et al.*, 1996].

Figure 23: Comparison with the MPI scheme using an observation acquired south of Newfoundland (39N, 57W) on January 30, 1993 at 14:34Z. This case corresponds to Figure 7 in [Hasselmann *et al.*, 1996].

Product examples

To meet the demands of end users for up-to-date wind and wave climate information the online service CLAMS has been set up. On this interactive web site, users can select their region of interest by the click of a mouse button. The CLAMS system subsequently gathers all satellite data recorded in that region over the years from a database. The user interface of CLAMS allows users to explore this data set in a number of ways. One option is to select a date of interest, and to plot a timeseries of the wind speed or significant wave height in the area. It is also possible to assess the climatic conditions in the area of interest: for instance the seasonal variation of either the wind speed or the wave height. Other options include the assessment of the different one-dimensional (Figure 24) and two-dimensional (Figure 25) distributions.

Not all users have expressed interest in using the Internet to get wind and wave climate data. Some because they want the climate tables in a format that can be imported in a spreadsheet, some because they are not familiar with the Internet. To satisfy these customers, an offline wind and wave climate service is being set up. The products that are made with this service largely comply with the ones in the CLAMS system. However, the fact that the service is offline allows for certain refinements that are impossible to implement in an online system. One of these includes the removal of the 180° ambiguity in the propagation direction of the swell. If the region of interest is sheltered by the nearby presence of land, it is often possible to resolve the ambiguity problem by simply assuming that the swell originated from the open ocean.

A few examples of offline wind and wave climate tables are shown in Table 4 and Table 5. The region of interest is the Bay of Khambhat along the North-Western coast of India. The presented tables show the conditions averaged over a year, based on 6 years of observations (1991-1997). Often the tables are also provided per month or per season.

Figure 24: Directional distribution of wave energy from SAR as visualized by the CLAMS system.

height of swell (m) in rows versus period of swell (s) in columns

	< 09	09 .10	10 .11	11 .12	12 .13	13 .14	14 .15	15 .16	16 .17	> 17
< 0.25	50	30	46	43	17	3	2	1	1	0
0.25 - 0.50	3	18	68	105	105	55	18	13	3	0
0.50 - 0.75	0	10	25	56	91	72	34	19	6	0
0.75 - 1.00	0	6	11	23	27	29	26	12	4	2
1.00 - 1.25	0	6	16	10	3	5	5	1	2	3
1.25 - 1.50	0	1	25	11	3	4	0	2	1	1
1.50 - 1.75	0	1	38	15	6	2	1	0	0	0
1.75 - 2.00	0	0	27	43	6	3	1	1	0	0
2.00 - 2.25	0	0	15	42	7	0	0	0	0	0
2.25 - 2.50	0	0	2	42	8	1	0	0	0	0
2.50 - 2.75	0	0	1	21	10	1	1	0	0	0
2.75 - 3.00	0	0	0	17	16	1	0	0	0	0
3.00 - 3.25	0	0	0	4	8	1	0	0	0	0
3.25 - 3.50	0	0	0	1	6	1	0	0	0	0
3.50 - 3.75	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0
3.75 - 4.00	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
> 4.00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Figure 25: Example of energy distribution of swell as function of wave height (rows) and period (columns) offered by CLAMS.

Table 4: Percentage per significant wave height/wind speed class. Period = all year, N = 46962.

speed [m/s] →	0-2	2-4	4-6	6-8	8-10	10-12	12-14	14-16	16-18	18-20	20-22	22-24
0.00 0.50	0.3	1.0	3.5	2.2	1.1	0.5	0.4	0.0				
0.50 1.00	0.9	2.9	9.1	6.1	2.8	1.4	6.5	0.1	0.0			
1.00 1.50	0.8	2.4	7.6	5.1	2.3	1.0	5.9	0.0	0.0	0.0		
1.50 2.00	0.4	1.0	3.4	2.3	1.1	0.5	2.4	0.0	0.0	0.0		
2.00 2.50	0.1	0.5	1.6	0.9	0.5	0.2	0.8					
2.50 3.00	0.2	0.8	2.4	1.7	0.8	0.3	1.2		0.0	0.0		
3.00 3.50	0.1	0.6	1.5	1.1	0.6	0.3	1.2	0.0	0.0			
3.50 4.00	0.1	0.5	1.3	0.8	0.4	0.2	0.9	0.0				
4.00 4.50	0.1	0.3	0.8	0.5	0.2	0.1	0.5	0.0				
4.50 5.00	0.0	0.1	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0				
5.00 5.50	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0					
5.50 6.00	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0								
6.00 6.50			0.0									

Table 5: Percentage of time per wind speed/direction class. Period = all year, N =37999.

direction →	0°-30°	30°-60°	60°-90°	90°-120°	120°-150°	150°-180°	180°-210°	210°-240°	240°-270°	270°-300°	300°-330°	330°-360°
0.0 2.0	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.29	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.30	0.3	0.4
2.0 4.0	2.1	0.8	0.5	0.16	0.21	0.17	0.13	0.4	2.4	2.6	1.4	1.8
4.0 6.0	6	1.6	0.8	0.28	0.10	0.05	0.14	1.1	8	10	6	5
6.0 8.0	4	1.5	0.4	0.27	0.12	0.03	0.09	1.9	6	5	4	2.6
8.0 10.0	1.8	0.4	0.10	0.11	0.07	0.15	0.05	2.6	5	1.0	0.5	0.3
10.0 12.0	0.3	0.14	0.02	0.02	0.07	0.19	0.01	1.9	2.6	0.3	0.02	0.02
12.0 14.0	0.05	0.02				0.03	0.00	0.5	0.5	0.02	0.01	
14.0 16.0								0.02	0.16			
16.0 18.0								0.00	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01
18.0 20.0									0.02		0.01	0.01

4.3 Wind and wave climatology from altimeter data

4.3.1 Wave Climate Data Visualisation for Operational Planning

Introduction

A wave climate data system, based on radar altimeter data, denoted CLAMS, has been developed at ARGOSS³. In the COASTMON project we have developed upon this system by aggregating the data into monthly mean, 10% exceedence and 90% exceedence values and integrating the data into a Geographical Information System (GIS). This product allows the user to browse the monthly wave climate spatial trends for the study area spanning between Ireland and Norway (Figure 26). The monthly data can be visualised in 2D, in 3D or as contours. The user can view a bar chart depicting the annual significant wave height or wind speed trends for any user-defined location. In addition the product incorporates an operational planning tool which identifies, over any selected time frame, areas which fall within user-defined limits of significant wave height and wind speed. We anticipate that this product will be of interest to marine operational planners for identifying windows of opportunity and to emergency response units to assist in the strategic planning of resource allocation.

³<http://clams.argoss.nl>

Figure 26: This image depicts the mean significant wave height values for December. This data is available for both significant wave and wind speed for each month in mean, 90% exceedence and 10% exceedence form.

Technical Description

The product is based on radar altimeter data providing significant wave height, H_s , derived from ERS-1, ERS-2 and Topex/Poseidon. In total 10 million measurements were used from the following periods:

ERS-1 Aug91-May96;

ERS-2 Jun95-Oct97;

T/P Oct92-Dec97

Significant wave height is calculated within a 0.5 degree grid, which spans 18W to 30E Longitude and 48N to 80N Latitude. The data were aggregated into monthly mean, 10% exceedence (10% of the values are below these values) and 90% exceedence (90% of the values are below these values). These data were output as Band Sequential Multiband (BSQ) images. They were imported into ArcView GIS. Since ArcView can only read positive integer values in BSQ format, the BSQ file values were multiplied by 100 to cater for decimal values. In ArcView the BSQ files were converted to a GRID format, a raster format native to, and therefore more flexibly handled by, the GIS. The grids were geo-referenced and projected into UTM to facilitate integration with the other datasets in the Cork COASTMON GIS.

The interface has been customised to allow easy browsing of the 6 datasets (Significant Wave Height monthly mean (h_s), 10% exceedence, 90% exceedence and Wind Speed (W_s) monthly mean, 10% exceedence and 90% exceedence). The datasets can be viewed as 0.5 degree grids or viewed in 3D with the height value representing the H_s or the W_s values, as shown in Figure 27, where the colour coding in this image represents the January wave height 90% exceedence data, however, the z axis represents the wind speed 90% exceedence values for the same months. This correlation of the two datasets facilitates spatial pattern analysis. Interpolated contour data can also be viewed (Figure 28). A visualisation tool has been developed which allows the user to view the temporal change for a user-selected 0.5 degree grid cell (Figure 29). The values are displayed for the selected months via a bar chart.

An operation planning tool has been developed which allows the user to integrate the significant wave height data with the wind speed data to help identify areas and periods suitable for weather sensitive maritime operations (Figure 30). The user is prompted for whether they want to base the analysis on the mean, the 10% exceedence or the 90% exceedence datasets. They are then prompted to select the month(s) of interest. They then enter the maximum Significant Wave Height and Wind Speed values allowable for the planned operation. Finally they identify the boundary of the area they are interested in. The tool returns a grid identifying suitable areas for the operation during that period.

Product examples

Figures 26–30 show examples of the output given by the visualization and operational planning tool.

Figure 27: This image demonstrates the versatility in visualising the data that the GIS lends this product. The image represents the January significant wave height 90% exceedence data, with the wave height represented in both the colour coding and in the z axis.

Figure 28: In this image the same significant wave height data is again depicted, however, in this example the data is represented by interpolated contours.

Figure 29: In addition to representing the entire study area on a monthly basis, a tool has been developed to enable the user to view the annual trend for individual 0.5 degree grid squares.

Figure 30: An operational planning tool has been produced which enables the user to identify areas within a user-specified location where the wind speed and significant wave height during a specific temporal period are suitable for undertaking sensitive maritime operations.

4.3.2 Intercomparison of wave model results and altimeter wave heights

Introduction

As part of the COASTMON project we have improved upon a GIS based Wave Atlas produced by the Hydraulics and Maritime Centre (HMRC) in Cork (Figure 31). The existing atlas visualises WAM modelled data for 8 offshore points around Ireland. In addition the system visualises inshore data derived from a local model which interpolates data to a 20m bathymetric contour around the coast. As part of the COASTMON project we have amended the system to enable a comparison to be undertaken between the significant wave height data derived from the WAM model and the data derived from the altimeter observations (Figure 32). This comparison can be undertaken via charts, tables or statistical summaries. The inshore model derived wave climate information has also been compared with SAR image derived wave climate. This aspect of the product is discussed in detail in section 4.2.2.

Technical details

The HMRC Wave Atlas system has been amended to run under the COASTMON Cork GIS. The CLAMS system was used to extract altimeter and scatterometer readings for the same locations and periods as are covered by the modelled data. The data was reformatted to correspond with the WAM derived data and the visualisation code amended to enable a comparison between the two data sources.

The HMRC have collaborated closely in the development of this produce and it is envisaged that they are potential end-users of the product as it enhances their existing system by allowing validation of their data by comparison with satellite observation data.

Product Examples

Figures 31–32 show screenshots of the wave atlas output.

Figure 31: In this image the Wave Atlas System informs over what period the data is available for both the model and the altimeter data (information boxes on left of screen). The yellow dot is the selected point about which the user is querying the data. The user is then prompted to enter a time period or a specific data.

Figure 32: In this example the system is comparing the significant wave height data for all of 1996 for the highlighted point. The data are depicted in chart form but could as easily be represented in tables or as summary statistics.

4.4 Bathymetry assessment

4.4.1 Application of the Bathymetry Assessment System in the Rosslare area

Introduction

Under favorable meteorological and hydrodynamical conditions features of the bottom topography of shallow seas show up on SAR images. The mechanism by which this happens is indirect, as the radar signal itself penetrates the water only a few millimeters. For moderate incidence angles, radar waves are reflected by short water waves on the surface. The presence of these waves is influenced by gradients in the tidal current, which in turn depends on the bottom topography. To describe this effect mathematical models have been developed. Inversion of these models makes it possible to retrieve topographical information from SAR imagery. Bathymetric surveys traditionally rely on *in situ* depth soundings. With the help of information from SAR imagery the number of traditional depth soundings necessary to produce a depth map of a given quality can be cut down significantly, which has obvious economical advantages.

In the COASTMON project the Bathymetry Assessment System (BAS) that is being developed by ARGOSS is applied to the coastal area near Rosslare in the South-East corner of Ireland. This area is suffering from a siltation problem and has been closely monitored over the past decades [Cracknell and Huang, 1988] [Huang and Davies, 1991]. An attempt will be made to enhance the coarse bathymetric information taken from digitized Admiralty charts. These charts are based on a combination of historical data, and on more recent information from harbor masters reported to the British Admiralty. For this purpose three ERS-1/2 SAR images of the area have been analyzed. The resulting depth map is compared with recent high resolution depth soundings that was carried out in 1997.

Technical description

The BAS system is being developed at ARGOSS to map the bottom topography of shallow seas from SAR images and a limited number of depth soundings. The method can be employed in situations with strong (tidal) currents (> 0.5 m/s) in combination with fair wind conditions (3 to 10 m/s). BAS requires the initial depth soundings for calibration purposes. The SAR imagery will be used to fill in the gaps between the initial depth soundings in way that is consistent with the information from the SAR image. The system consists of two parts: an imaging model suite to compute a SAR image for a given depth map and tidal information, and an inversion scheme. A simulated radar image is calculated from a first-guess depth map using the forward model. The difference between the observed and simulated image is expressed in terms of a cost function. In an iterative procedure the depth map is adjusted until the difference between the simulated and observed radar image is minimal.

Based on admiralty charts of the region, an initial depth map was constructed (Figure 34). Three ERS-1/2 SAR images were selected that showed bottom features. These images were acquired on 16 April 1993, 5 April 1997 and 14 April 1997. Details of the images showing the region of interest near Rosslare are shown in Figure 33.

Figure 33: Radar images of the Rosslare area acquired on 16 April 1993 (left), 5 April 1997 (middle) and 14 April 1997 (right). On the top row the depth contours obtained from the admiralty chart are superimposed.

Product examples

The combination of the initial depth map (Figure 34) with the three SAR images in the BAS system resulted in a revised depth map (Figure 35). Comparing the two figures, we see that the SAR imagery has smoothed the depth chart that was based on the interpolation between depth contours from the admiralty chart. The profiles shown in the figures 36 and 37 give a more detailed picture of the effect of the satellite imagery. In particular the second figure shows that the SAR enhances certain bottom features. In the vicinity of $y = 5797$ three wiggles in the depth are detected, that have an estimated amplitude of several meters.

In the region where reference depth soundings are available, the bottom left corner of the image, the SAR imagery show little detail. Consequently the SAR enhanced depth map is not altered in this region.

Figure 34: Color coded depth map based on admiralty chart.

Figure 35: Depths from the admiralty chart enhanced with the SAR imagery.

Figure 36: Depth profile along the horizontal line $y = 5797.5$. The SAR imagery has smoothed the depths based on the admiralty chart, and has shifted the location of the depth maximum slightly.

Figure 37: Depth profile along the column $x = 690$. The most interesting feature introduced by the SAR imagery are the wiggles in the vicinity of $y = 5797$. The first two SAR images in Figure 33 clearly show these features.

4.4.2 Seasonal maps identifying locations suitable for the application of the BAS Technique

Introduction

After the first attempt to implement the Bathymetric Assessment from SAR (BAS) technique in Cork Harbour, we recognised the importance of producing a series of seasonal maps/datasets which give an initial indication of where the technique could potentially be used. The technique's applicability is constrained by bathymetry, wind speed and current strength. In this product we have used the COASTMON Cork GIS to correlate these datasets, or proxies for these identified where the data were not available, and identified areas where the technique could be applied. In addition, we have integrated a database of SAR availability metadata, which can be used to access information about SAR availability for any user-defined location.

Technical Description

The constraining factors to the successful application of the BAS technique are:

- Tidal current of greater than 0.5 m/s;
- Wind speed of greater than or equal to 3 m/s and less than or equal to 10m/s;
- Bathymetry of less than or equal to 50m.

To produce this product we accessed the following datasets:

- 50m contour data digitised by the Irish Marine Data Centre from British Admiralty Charts;
- the 20 and 30 cm/sec contours of maximum tidal current amplitudes taken from the BODC UKDMAP (originally derived from *the Atlas of Tidal Elevations and Currents around the British Isles*, Howarth, M,J, 1990);
- the monthly wind speed grid data derived from the Wave Climate Data Visualisation for Operational Planning product as discussed above, aggregated into seasonal averages;
- SAR availability metadata obtained from DESCW.

The current data is very generalised but in the absence of any other available information it has been used in this version of the product. The tidal diamonds on the British Admiralty Charts would provide more detailed information; however, this data is not available in a digital form. We are currently in discussion with the Irish Marine Data Centre about the possibility of accessing a digitised version of this data that they hold.

The scatterometer derived wind speed data is primarily intended for offshore use. Due to the resolution of the data used there is no data for Cork Harbour. In the absence of data for the Harbour itself, its suitability is ambiguous, but called into doubt by its adjacency to an area of unsuitability to the East. The Irish Meteorological Office was approached for more detailed inshore data. However, their wind speed observations are very site specific and they were not

Figure 38: Seasonal map for the spring.

able to supply us with a more generalised version for the entire coastline. We believe that the scatterometer derived wind speed data can be used in this application with the caveat that the data is indicative of inshore wind speeds rather than representative.

The current and wind speed datasets were converted into raster grids and queried to identify areas where the current is greater than 0.5 m/s and the wind speed is greater than or equal to 3 m/s and less than or equal to 10 m/s. The 4 resulting seasonal datasets were overlaid with the 50 m bathymetric contour to demarcate the extent of where the water is shallow enough to allow the method to be viable. The SAR availability database has been converted into an Arcview shapefile that can then be overlaid. This allows the user to access information about all the available imagery for the area that they have now identified as suitable for the technique.

We anticipate that this product will be of value to all potential BAS end-users in Ireland (outlined in detail in section 4.4.1) as this will enable them to make a first guess as to the applicability of the technique to their area of interest.

Product Examples

Figure 38 shows an example of a seasonal map of areas where the BAS technique is likely to be applicable. The low level of current off the North and West coast restricts the use of this technique to the SE coast. The initial unsuccessful use of the BAS technique in the Cork Harbour area could have been avoided by use of this tool. The Rosslare area in the SE of the country, used in the second COASTMON BAS trial should be suitable all year round for the application of the technique. Once the area of applicability has been ascertained, the tool can be used to identify which SAR images are most suitable for use in the area.

4.5 Currents, fronts, and water quality

4.5.1 Current model results and comparison using EO

In the Norwegian study area, the effect of ocean currents can be important in the navigation of very large crude-oil carriers (VLCCs) and other large vessels and offshore structures. The open sea adjacent to the Norwegian coast is subject to the influence of the Norwegian coastal current, which generally flows northwards, but in which eddies occur which may cause extreme currents of up to 1.5 m/s. It is thus important to have an indication of the spatial gradients in the current when passing through the straits separating the open waters from the fjords and inshore waters.

The Norwegian Meteorological Institute (DNMI) operates a three-dimensional numerical ocean current model (ECOM3D), with 20 km grid cells, on a routine basis, and an example of the model results during the COASTMON demonstration period is shown in Figure 39. Although the resolution is coarse, it can be clearly seen that the current near the west coast of Norway is distinctly different from that further from the shore.

Figure 39: Current at 10 m depth from the ECOM3D operational model with 20 km resolution, 1998 February 10, 06h UTC (6-hour forecast). The box in the upper left corner of the plot shows the area where the 4 km resolution model is tested.

Figure 40: Current at 10 m depth from the hydrodynamic model with 4 km resolution, 1998 February 10, 00h UTC (forced by analysed meteorological fields). The location of this high resolution model is west of Haltenbanken, as shown in Figure 39.

DNMI's high resolution ocean model, with 4 km grid cells, can simulate more detailed patterns of the current field such as eddies and meanders within a limited area. Example of output from the high-resolution model is shown in Figure 40.

Such eddy features in the current can be seen in satellite optical and infra-red images, but these are restricted by the presence of cloud cover. SAR images, such as the one shown in Figure 41, also show eddying features in considerable detail, under given environmental conditions.

It is not possible to directly determine the current velocity and direction from the observed features, although many details of current structures can be seen in SAR images, and the theory for the radar imaging of these structures, by means of the interaction of waves, currents, and wind, is well developed. However, it was found possible to evaluate the performance of various numerical models which provide 'indicative' results.

Original SAR data © ESA/TSS 1997

Figure 41: 100×100 km ERS-2 SAR image of the West Norwegian coast, 1998 January 15. The outlet of Sognefjord is near the centre of the image. The main feature to be seen is eddying and frontal structures in the Norwegian coastal current.

Original SAR data © ESA/TSS 1995

Figure 42: ERS-2 SAR image from 11h UTC on 1995 September 27 during the COAST WATCH '95 experiment. The acoustic Doppler current profiler current measurements from the ship, which moved from south to north along the track, are shown by the arrows.

During the COASTWATCH '95 experiment conducted in the autumn of 1995 off the southern coast of Norway, SAR ocean features were investigated using ship and buoy observations of oceanographic and meteorological parameters [Johannessen *et al.*, 1997] [Korsbakken *et al.*, 1998].

Figure 42 shows an example of simultaneous SAR and current data collected during the COASTWATCH '95 experiment. The dark wedge-shaped feature at about 57.9° is a cold-water westward-flowing jet associated with upwelling. The research vessel crossed the front at

the south-west side of the jet within a few minutes of the time the SAR image was taken. A peak in the radar backscatter of about 2 dB was observed at the front, and is likely to be due to the enhancement of short surface capillary waves caused by the current shear of about 50 cm/s across the front, as measured by the ship-borne acoustic current profiler.

To investigate this, a number of radar simulation runs were made using the ERIM Ocean Model (EOM), which simulates both the wave-current interaction effects and the electromagnetic wave scattering at the sea surface. The model was also amended to take account of wave breaking processes generating extra centimetre-scale waves. However, the model only predicted a small radar backscatter enhancement (≈ 0.4 dB) when the observed current field was used. If an artificially ‘sharpened’ current field with the same change in current but over a shorter distance was used (50 m, rather than the 1.7 km over which the observed current could be resolved), the backscatter enhancement increased to approximately 1 dB, and this figure could be further increased if a component of convergence at the front was added to the shear.

To make further progress at a fundamental level in improving this radar backscattering modelling product for the SAR expression of current-related features, it may be necessary to use more sophisticated wave generation/evolution, wave-current interaction (including the effect of wave breaking), and radar backscattering models. However, for practical purposes we may still need to trace ‘features’ from image to image in order to estimate currents quantitatively. There is still a requirement for more detailed experimental evaluation of the model simulations. *In situ* measurement of surface currents needs to be performed at small spatial scales (finer than 10 m resolution) to validate these models, and detailed observations of short wind waves and atmospheric boundary layer parameters also need to be made.

4.5.2 Sea surface temperature and ocean frontal features

It has been possible to determine sea surface temperatures from satellites since infrared radiometers became available on satellites in the 1970's. The main limitation is cloudcover, which inhibits observation of the sea surface most of the time in Northern Europe. Currently, sea surface temperatures are operationally available from NOAA AVHRR and ERS-2 ATSR, among others, both with a spatial resolution of about 1 km.

The algorithm currently used to derive sea surface temperature is due to [Lauritson *et al.*, 1979]. The radiance is computed from channels 4 or 5 using the two-point linear radiance calibration available from the on-board blackbody and space-view signals, with a nonlinearity correction. The Planck equation and sensor spectral function are used to convert to temperature. Cloud screening is important [Saunders and Kriebel, 1988]. The algorithm has a sensitivity of 0.1–0.2 K, and has less noise than other multichannel algorithms for SST determination.

Comments by end users at the Norwegian user workshop indicate that it is very important to provide interpretations of images supplied to the users. This is indicated in Figure 43 by the temperature scale, and the annotation, indicating the presence of clouds, the direction of the coastal current, and the position of an eddy at an end of a jet in the current. The precise nature of the annotation obviously depends on the end user's particular requirements.

Figures 44–45 show an AVHRR quick-look and SAR images from respectively September 25 and 29, 1997, off the south-west of Ireland. There are indications of a temperature front in the AVHRR image, which correspond to the location of some frontal features (bright lines) shown in the SAR. The frontal structures and internal waves shown in Figure 45 are near the edge of the continental shelf (shelf break), where the sea bottom topography changes sharply, and causes such dynamic phenomena.

Figure 43: A full-resolution AVHRR image calibrated to give sea-surface temperature values. The position of the Norwegian coastal current is given by its associated cooler water, and a more intense jet with an eddy at its tip is also shown. A quicklook database at Dundee Satellite Receiving Station is useful to search for cloud-free NOAA AVHRR images (URL: <http://www.sat.dundee.ac.uk/auth.html>).

Original AVHRR data © NOAA 1997

Figure 44: NOAA AVHRR quick-look, 1997 September 25, 07:41 UTC, showing sea-surface temperature variations (a brighter feature indicated by the arrow) near the south-west coast of Ireland.

Original SAR data © ESA/UK-PAF 1997

Figure 45: ERS-2 SAR SLCI (Single Look Complex Image), West coast of Ireland, 1997 September 29, 11:40 UTC, Descending orbit. The frontal features observed in the AVHRR image (Figure 44) is located in an area of internal waves observed in the SAR image.

4.5.3 Algal bloom

The application of EO data to Algal Bloom Monitoring, an Irish case study

Since the late 1970s there has been a dramatic increase in finfish and shellfish farming in Ireland. The production of farmed salmon has increased from 21 tonnes in 1980 to 11,600 tonnes in 1994. While over the same time the production of rope cultured mussels, *Mytilus edulis*, has increased from 175 tonnes to 4,700 tonnes while the production of the Pacific oyster *Crassostrea gigas* has increased from 60 tonnes to 2,000 tonnes.

The presence of harmful or toxic algal blooms negatively impacts on the aquaculture industry. The algae affect aquaculture production by causing mass mortalities in fish as a result of gill damage, deoxygenation during bloom decay or toxin production. In contrast to the wild fish, the aquaculture fish has no or limited escape possibilities to avoid the harmful algae blooms. Indirect effects can be due to the accumulation of toxins in shellfish under certain circumstances, rendering them unsafe for human consumption.

Current monitoring in Ireland involves a programme to monitor the presence of natural phytoplankton toxins in Irish shellfish and the analysis of seawater for the presence of toxin producing phytoplankton. The programme is designed to detect toxicity in shellfish growing areas before harvesting, thereby providing information to restrict the placing of toxic shellfish on the market. The current monitoring strategy for bloom events adopted by the Fisheries Research Centre (Marine Institute) is a reactive rather than a proactive one. Earth observational data in the form of MOS⁴, SeaWiFS, AVHRR and SAR data could be integrated to provide an early warning system for bloom monitoring in Ireland.

It is with this primary objective in mind that we have looked at a number of significant algal bloom events that have occurred in the south west of Ireland over the last number of years. We have attempted to utilise AVHRR (movement of water masses, location of fronts), SAR (location of fronts and surface films) and MOS imagery (location of algal blooms and oceanographic fronts). These were utilised independently and/or collectively to learn more about the dynamics of these bloom events and to assess the suitability of EO data in the monitoring of these harmful algal blooms (HABs) in Ireland. The two bloom events that we looked at include:

- *Noctiluca scintillans* bloom event in the Kenmare Bay/Bantry Bay area that was recorded between 23–29 September 1997. This was clearly visible and gave a bright orange/yellow colour to the water. Cell counts of up to 2.4 million cells/litre were recorded.
- *Alexandrium tamarense*, a PSP toxin producer, which occurred in Cork Harbour around 24 June 1996. Cell counts of up to 850,000 cells/litre were recorded. [Personnel Communication Dr. Terry McMahon, Fisheries Research Centre].

⁴The MOS (Modular Optoelectronic Scanner) sensor is a spaceborne imaging spectrometer for the visible and near infrared part of the spectrum built by DLR Institute for Space Sensor Technology in Germany. The sensor was launched on board the Indian Remote Sensing Satellite IRS-P3 in March 1996. The sensor has 13 channels in the visible and near-infrared (408 - 1010 nm), making the sensor ideal for the remote sensing of coastal zones, where the wide variety of water constituents make analysis of spectral data more complex. The resolution is roughly 1 km, and the swath width is 200 km. In comparison, the American SeaWiFS has only 8 channels (412 - 865 nm), a similar resolution and a swath width of 2000 km.

We would hope that the information gained from such a study could be utilised by the Fisheries Research Centre to assist them in the design of a monitoring system for algal blooms, by allowing them to:

- Act in a proactive rather than reactive manner
- Provide a forecasting service with respect to the movement (advection) of algal bloom events
- Enabling the aquaculture industry to harvest shellfish / finfish before the arrival of harmful algal blooms thus minimising the economic and health impacts of the blooms in the region

The features in the MOS image shown in Figure 46 coincide geographically with the approximate location of the Irish Shelf Front [Huang and Davies, 1991]. The Irish Shelf Front, whose location can be defined by the 35.3 isohaline, separates Irish coastal waters from oceanic waters further offshore. The surface signature of the Irish Shelf Front lies between 20 and 35 km off the coast at about 51°30'N. It is thought that the front is a major influence on the physical and biological processes off south west Ireland. This front again appears to be quite evident in the SAR imagery taken on the 29th of September 1997 (Figure 45).

Figure 46: MOS image obtained on 3rd May 1998 possibly depicting the presence of the Irish Shelf Front (in the lower part of the image), which has a major influence on physical and biological processes in the region.

Figure 47: MOS imagery of Southern Ireland showing a large bloom event on 3rd May 1998 (bright area in the lower, right part of the image). The white areas are clouds.

Table 6: Recent algae blooms in Irish waters causing closures of shellfish growing areas.

Year	Duration of closure
1984	August - October
1985	No closure
1986	No closure
1987	August - December
1988	June - November
1989	June - September
1990	July - October
1991	June - November
1992	June - September
1993	June - September
1994	May - February
1995	June - September
1996	September

A Recent Shellfish Closure

The need for an algal bloom monitoring system is evident by the frequency and duration of closures of shellfish growing areas in Ireland due to the presence of DSP toxins (Table 6).

The recent closure of the mussel production area in Bantry Bay in early May, 1998 was based on a positive bioassay test for the presence of Diarrhetic Shellfish Poison (DSP) toxins in a sample of mussels from the area. Following two further negative weekly test results the area was re-opened. The positive result was not associated with an algal bloom event.

MOS imagery obtained by ARGOSS during the recent period in which the shellfish fishery in Bantry was closed shows features which can be interpreted as large algal events both along the coast and offshore (Figure 47). Communication with the Fisheries Research Centre indicated the following:

*On the 7th May we got a report of discoloured water in the Union Hall/ Glandore area from a local fisherman (Colin Barnes) and on the 8th May we went down and took several samples and photographs. The water was very green and all the samples contained *Phaeocystis* spp. that we have identified as *Phaeocystisglobosa*. It is more than likely therefore that the 'green patch' in the area south of Cork and along the Cork coast shown on the image taken on the 3rd May is showing the extent of this bloom. We were not aware that the bloom was so geographically extensive.*

The availability of images like this really helps in mapping the extent of the bloom, which would be virtually impossible with conventional sampling methods. [Personnel Communication, Dr. Terry McMahon, Fisheries Research Centre].

Original SAR data © ESA/TSS 1997

Figure 48: Subscene of ERS-2 SAR image from 19 December 1997 covering an area of 30 by 30 km in the North Sea, some 80 km west-southwest of Fedje. Bright spots in the SAR image indicating platforms or supply ships on the Troll platform field are marked in the annotation on the right, as are linear features representing dark backscatter signatures.

4.5.4 Surface slicks and oil spill monitoring

Oil slicks are observable in SAR images as dark signatures. However, several other man-made and natural phenomena give rise to similar signatures making the detection of oil slicks a complicated operation. Nevertheless, a lot of progress has been made in this field and the State Pollution Control Authority (SFT) in Norway routinely uses interpreted SAR images provided by TSS in their oil spill surveillance [Wahl *et al.*, 1994]. Potential oil spill signatures, their location, time, shape and extent, are reported to SFT's operational surveillance aircraft. The aircraft may then perform a dedicated flight to check the potential spill location. This both improves the monitoring capability and increases the efficiency in use of aircraft flight hours.

SAR is able to image ocean surface films caused by the presence of natural surfactant materials. These give rise to areas of reduced backscatter, in the same way as oil spills do, but their intensity and also the shapes of the film areas can usually be distinguished visually from those of oil slicks. The potential importance of SAR observations of natural surface films in monitoring biological activity in coastal waters, for the benefit of fisheries and aquaculture interests is currently investigated. Study of several hundred SAR images shows that natural surface films are generally more common in biologically productive coastal waters than in the open ocean.

Surface slicks observed during the COASTMON project

On 19 December 1997 a full resolution ERS-2 SAR scene was obtained from Tromsø Satellite Station (TSS), and a subscene of this image is shown in Figure 48. The bright spots on the SAR image are from oil platforms and supply or transportation ships in the Troll platform area in the North Sea. The dark signatures connected to some of these spots are believed to be produced water (i.e. water that was pumped up from the reservoir together with the oil during production), as similar signature have been observed in this area before, and it is known that the production platforms release produced water [Espedal, 1998]. In Figure 48, the production platform is located farthest north, while a gas platform is located in the right part of the image.

Original SAR data © ESA/TSS 1996

Figure 49: Subscene of the ERS-2 SAR image from the North Sea on 30 April 1996 (10:47GMT), the necessary wind history, sketches of the slick shape when exposed to low winds causing the slick to diffuse, and the available wind history from a selected point (below). The subscene covers about 10x10km.

Surface slicks in the North Sea

Other studies have shown that knowledge of the wind history is useful when analysing SAR images for potential oil spills [Hamre *et al.*, 1997, Hamre *et al.*, 1995]. A subset of an ERS-2 image from 30 April 1996 centered around 57.7°N, 4.5°E is shown in Figure 49. The angular slick shape is typical for an oil spill which has been exposed to shifting wind directions. Use of the wind history analysis supports this assumption, even if the slick has a slightly different shape as the diffusion of part b (see Figure 49, right) is closest to the source instead of closest to the bend.

Figure 50 shows another ERS-2 SAR image with slicks, and its associated wind history. The SAR image contains a slick which is clearly distinct from its surroundings. This slick is connected to a bright spot which is the Ula platform in the Norwegian sector of the North Sea [Hamre *et al.*, 1995]. The sharp angle of the slick makes it a likely candidate for oil spills.

By looking at the wind history, we find that the wind changed direction (at time T1; in Figure 50, from north-western to western, about 2 hours before the image was taken (at time T2). This change of wind direction corresponds to the sharp bend of the slick, meaning that the part of the slick connected to the platform was generated after the wind turned, while the longest part of the slick is older. Before 06:00GMT on November 25 the slick was exposed to a wind of about 7.5m/s for at least 3 hours, and probably longer since the wind the day before was about 15m/s at noon. If the slick contained natural film, it would have been broken up

Figure 50: Example of angular winding slick in SAR imagery (25.11.94, 10:50GMT) and associated wind history. Image size is 25 km by 25 km.

and dispersed by the strong wind. This slick however, remains connected, and has a sharp gradient to the surrounding area. Thus, the wind history indicates that the slick is man-made and was generated before 09:00GMT (when the wind turned). The shape of the slick shows that much of the material was released before the wind direction changed, as the part of the slick generated before the wind turned is about twice as long as the part generated afterwards. From the wind history, as given in Figure 50, we deduce that the slick may be nearly a day old, since there was another significant change in wind direction at that time but no corresponding bend on the slick.

Based on the analysis presented above, we conclude that the slick is man-made, at least 2 hours old and maximum 23 hours old. With a more detailed wind history, it might be possible to determine the age of the slick more accurately. This particular slick was confirmed to contain oil or oil-based material [Espedal *et al.*, 1995], due to problems with a drilling well on the Ula platform. However, no information was available on how long these problems lasted, or how much oil or oil-based material were released into the ocean.

4.6 Synergy of EO techniques

Introduction

In collaboration with the University of Southampton, NERSC performed a study for ESA on The synergetic use of infrared, optical and microwave remote sensing observations, for both open ocean and coastal areas. NERSC is applying to COASTMON the results of this study in the use of combinations of different EO techniques to enhance the value of the data products.

Table 7 shows the types of synergetic remote sensing techniques investigated, and their value.

Product examples

Figure 51 is a NOAA AVHRR thermal infra-red image sequence at 24-hour intervals south of Norway, showing the evolution of the eddies in the Norwegian coastal current (the dark, low sea-surface temperature region, in which the flow is generally toward the west) and the eddies and fronts associated with it. In the Tandem phase of ERS-1 and ERS-2 (May 1995 — May 1996), it was also possible on occasion to obtain SAR images at a 24-hour (or closer) separation. An example of such a sequence is shown in Figure 52, and a number of fronts between different water masses can also be seen as rather bright boundaries around 30–50 km south-west of the Norwegian coast. The combined AVHRR/SAR image (Figure 53) shows how the frontal features are associated with sea-surface temperature changes.

Figure 54 shows a concept of how one may take advantage of remote sensing synergy for pilot monitoring systems.

Table 7: Examples of synergetic remote sensing

Synergy	Phenomena detected/ measured	Result of study
SAR, thermal IR and altimeter (TOPEX/-POSEIDON)	Sea-surface height, meso-scale circulation features	The potential advantages of synergy remain speculative
SAR and thermal IR	large & meso-scale circulation features,	Useful complementary information, can be associated with bathymetry
ERS-1,2 SAR tandem	Highly dynamic features such as current fronts	Synergy advantageous, though interpretation remains speculative

Original AVHRR data © NOAA 1995

Figure 51: NOAA AVHRR thermal infra-red image sequence south of Norway, 1995 September 19–21.

Original SAR data © ESA/TSS 1995

Figure 52: ERS-1/2 SAR tandem pair from south-southwest of Norway, 1995 September 30.

Original SAR data © ESA/TSS 1995 Original AVHRR data © NOAA 1995

Figure 53: Synergetic use of AVHRR thermal infra-red and ERS-1 SAR data south of Norway, 1995 September 30.

Figure 54: Concept of a pilot monitoring system in a synergetic remote sensing perspective.

5 Summary of results

The development of EO-data products for coastal waters has been focused on the following five products: (1) high resolution wind field from SAR, (2) wave data products, (3) wind and wave climatology from altimeter data, (4) shallow water bathymetric charts, and (5) a group of SAR-derived products mapping features such as currents, fronts and oil spills. In addition, the use of visual/IR satellite imagery for detection of algal blooms and some cases of synergetic use of EO data were investigated. An assessment of each type of product is given below, based on feedback from potential users contacted during the project, and experiences made in other projects.

High resolution wind field from SAR

An improved algorithm for derivation of wind speed from SAR images was developed during the COASTMON project. This SAR wind algorithm (SWA) is based on the spectral properties of full-resolution images. The algorithm is based on a relation between the smearing effects in the SAR image and the wind field, and does not require absolute calibration of the radar data [Korsbakken *et al.*, 1998]. Using high resolution ERS SAR data, wind fields can be derived on scales down to a few hundred meters. The algorithm has been tested in Norwegian coastal waters for wind speeds between 5 m/s and 14 m/s, and the accuracy of the algorithm varied between ± 1 -2 m/s and up to ± 5 -6 m/s by comparing with in situ wind measurements [Korsbakken *et al.*, 1998].

Users of high resolution wind fields such as meteorological institutes, ship traffic managers and harbour authorities, Navy and Coast Guard vessels and offshore industry, all require frequent and regular data, typically 2-4 times per day, to support their operational work. This cannot be satisfied with today's satellites, where a typical revisit period is 3 days. Hence, more satellites are needed to meet the need for more frequent data. The advantage of SAR-derived wind is the high-resolution wind fields which are more detailed and accurate than the standard meteorological wind products. The SAR images can provide wind fields gridded to a few km. The altimeter on the other hand, cannot provide such detailed data about local wind conditions, and is not well suited for users in ship traffic management or route planning. The offshore industry, such as oil companies, are also interested in statistical data, i.e. wind climate data, and such data requirements are more likely to be met by the currently available satellites.

Wave data products

Significant wave height can be derived from satellite altimeter data, for use in operational wave forecasting [Breivik *et al.*, 1998]. The resolution of the wave height estimates from altimeter along the track is about 7 km. The wave field is a gridded data set developed by a wave model using altimeter as one of the input data.

During the COASTMON demonstration period (December 1997 - February 1998), a land based radar was placed near Fedje VTS Center, and from these measurements directive wave spectrums were estimated. Such spectra can also be estimated by a wave model (WINCH) and from ERS SAR data. A comparison between the resulting spectra from the different sources was made, and showed that the wave model estimates were in good agreement with the measured

data, while the spectra derived from only SAR data were less accurate. The best results are obtained when satellite data are used in combination with modelling.

Coastal surveyance and engineering activities require a high spatial resolution, which is best met by derival of wave spectra from SAR data. Other users, such as meteorological institutes, are also interested in detailed data for generating high resolution forecasts in e.g. the coastal zone.

The main limiting factor for generation of high resolution wave products are the lack of daily (or better) coverage with the satellittes available today. Obtaining data from a land based radar may be an alternative for organisations needing information about a small area, but is not practical for surveyance of larger areas extending several hundred km from the coast.

Wind and wave climatology from altimeter data

To meet the needs of marine operational planners and emergency response units, a wave climate data system based on altimeter data was further developed and customised for the Irish application sites. This system, named CLAMS, was extended to show monthly statistics and these data were integrated in a GIS, for use in conjunction with other oceanographic and meteorological data. The products provided by CLAMS are used as a valuable tool for planning marine operations.

The radar altimeter provides good coverage for generation of large scale climatological data and routines for extracting such information for a specific area can be set up. Examples of such products are monthly mean significant wave height and wind speeds for the coast of Ireland.

Shallow water bathymetric charts

The Bathymetry Assessment System (BAS) has been developed to enable users to obtain detailed bathymetric maps of coastal regions by means of SAR data and without extensive use of in situ measurements. The BAS has been tested for Dutch and Irish coastal areas in this project. The BAS technique is constrained by the following factors: (1) the tidal current must be >0.5 m/s, (2) the wind speed must be ≥ 3 m/s and <10 m/s, and (3) the depth must be ≤ 50 m. These conditions were satisfied for the Rosslare area on the East coast of Ireland, and the technique was successfully applied to a set of SAR images. By comparing with the British Admiralty Charts, it was found that the BAS generated bathymetry was in good accordance with the map generated from field measurements. The BAS technique was also successfully used in Dutch coastal areas, and customers are also interested in applying it in other parts of the world, e.g. in Asia.

SAR-derived products mapping features such as currents, fronts and oil spills

Ocean fronts, eddies and current patterns in coastal waters have been frequently observed in SAR images. During the COASTWATCH'95 field experiment the correspondence between frontal features observed in the SAR image and measured gradients in the surface current field, was investigated showing that SAR ocean fronts can be associated with horisontal gradients

in the surface velocity. Unfortunately, ocean current cannot be quantitatively derived from SAR data, and hence the comparison with either field data or estimates from a numerical ocean model can only be done on a qualitative basis. The advantage of SAR data is the good capability to map current flow patterns synoptically over larger areas.

Oil on the ocean surface will dampen out the capillary waves that reflects the radar signal, and hence oil spills can be seen as dark features in SAR images when the wind conditions are favourable (approx. 3-10 m/s). On a SAR scene from 19 December 1997 several dark features were observed close to oil platforms seems as bright spots in the image. Based on the signature and shape of the slicks, they are believed to be produced water (i.e. water that comes from the reservoir together with the oil during production). SAR oil spill monitoring is run as an operational service in Norway as an integrated part of The State Pollution Control Authority's aircraft survey.

Algal blooms

Algal bloom occur regularly in Irish ocean areas and can be a large problem to e.g. fish farmers. Being able to detect and track the motion of an algal bloom is therefore important. Two events of known algal blooms, one in June 1996 and one in September 1997, were investigated.

Algal blooms can be detected in visual/IR satellite imagery, e.g. in AVHRR, MOS and SeaWiFS data. These data are available on a regular basis, but their use is limited by cloud conditions.

Synergetic EO products

In addition to the products described above, synergetic use of EO techniques has also been demonstrated in Norwegian waters, with the combination of SAR and AVHRR data for detection and analysis of large and meso-scale ocean circulation features as the most promising.

Other combinations of EO data can also provide useful information, but further investigation is needed to develop products of interest for the users. Synoptic EO-products will in principle extract information from different sources and provide an overall better product compared to what a single sensor can do.

Overall conclusion

This work has demonstrated the feasibility of using selected EO-data for the COASTMON application sites.

The results showed that:

- Useful data products for coastal and marine operations can be generated from several existing EO data (SAR, altimeter, AVHRR, etc.), given that certain meteorological or other conditions imposed by the specific algorithm are met.
- SAR is capable of providing high resolution images suited for coastal monitoring, and has the advantage of being independent of daylight and clouds. Examples of products that can be developed from SAR data are high resolution wind fields, wave products,

detection of frontal structures and monitoring of oil spills. The main limiting factor is the insufficient temporal and spatial resolution provided by today's satellites.

- The radar altimeter is well suited for providing climatological wind and wave data on large and regional scales, but its spatial resolution does not suffice for many activities in the coastal zone, e.g. harbour monitoring.
- Visual/IR sensors are useful for monitoring of algal blooms and water quality parameters, but their use is limited by clouds implying that temporal coverage is poor. On the other hand the spatial resolution (1 km) is adequate for such monitoring purposes.
- Users can be grouped in two main categories: operational and occasional users who need data for planning. The first need 'continuous' data in near real-time, while the latter may be satisfied with climatological data. More satellites are needed to provide sufficient coverage in the coastal zone.
- The users can also be categorized into: those needing local, very detailed information and those needing regional coverage but at a lower resolution. The first group need high resolution data, i.e. on the order of meters, while the other group can do with data on the order of a few kilometers.
- Spatial resolution is adequate for SAR and AVHRR data, while the altimeter data are too coarse near the coast.
- Temporal resolution is poor for customers who need frequent data coverage.

Future trends:

- More SAR satellites and improved SAR technology (polarimetric, multi-mode, multichannel).
- Hyperspectral data with high resolution.

Acknowledgements

In addition to support from the European Commission under Contract ENV4-CT96-0360, this work was supported by the European Space Agency (ESA) under Contract 11969/96/NL/CN, and the Norwegian Research Council under project 133922/720. ERS SAR data were obtained under ESA projects AOT.N302 and AO3-281, and RADARSAT data under the Announcement of Opportunity for RADARSAT. We thank W. Knoepfl and Susanne Lehner for the supply of data processing and calibration software for SAR data⁵.

⁵GEOS utilities for input and re-calibration of CEOS formatted SAR data, `getit` and `calit` version 4.3, last update 16-Jul-1998, W. Knoepfl

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